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ASTRAL'S OCEAN LITERACY FOR AQUACULTURE: INCREASING PUBLIC ACCEPTANCE AND AWARENESS OF AQUACULTURE IN THE ATLANTIC

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ASTRAL (*All Atlantic Ocean Sustainable, Profitable and Resilient Aquaculture*) is a Horizon 2020 project focused on integrated multi-trophic aquaculture (IMTA) farming, aiming to define, support, and promote this type of sustainable aquaculture production across the Atlantic area. IMTA is the farming of species from different trophic levels in a way that allows one species' uneaten feed and wastes to be used as inputs (fertilisers and feed) for another species. Sharing knowledge and capacity development are among ASTRAL priorities, as well as to build a collaborative ecosystem along the Atlantic Ocean with industrial partners, SMEs, scientists, policymakers, social representatives, and other relevant stakeholders.

ASTRAL is committed to increasing the public acceptance and awareness of aquaculture by fostering public understanding of the value of aquaculture and especially IMTA, as a sustainable way to produce aquatic products. The project is also committed to reinforcing existing international efforts to advance acceptance and awareness about the sustainable exploitation of marine resources. ASTRAL works with a multilayer stakeholder's approach, therefore different Ocean Literacy activities have been designed around the project to ensure that the message reaches all the sectors of interest.

For example, targeting a wide public, specific campaigns in ocean literacy have been developed around the importance of safe and nutritious aquaculture seafood and addressing climate change resilience and ocean influence. During the World Ocean Day 2021, ASTRAL organised, in a coastal fishing community in Lagos (Nigeria), a variety of activities which included: 1) a clean-up campaign with the Makoko fishing community, 2) a thematic session about 'The Ocean and Livelihoods' and 3) training on 'Waste upcycling and women empowerment (Fig.1).

To engage a younger generation, during the Ideation Days 2022 at Terceira Island (Azores, Portugal), different activities were carried out specifically designed for secondary school students (Fig. 2). The activities were focused on science and innovation, including short thematic talks and a Bootcamp to promote in the audience the spirit of innovation and the creation of ideas. ASTRAL introduced the importance of Sustainable Food Production, explaining to the young audience concepts such as trophic level, carbon footprint, sustainability, and food security, and how IMTA contributes to sustainable food production.

Other examples of targeted Ocean Literacy campaigns are those addressing specific issues and engaging selected stakeholders, as in the case of women working in aquaculture. 70% of the global aquaculture workforce is female, nevertheless, the great majority of management of the production is undertaken by men. The lack of data on women in aquaculture and gender-oriented training is one reason why women are invisible in aquaculture policy. ASTRAL is working to reduce this unbalance by empowering women in the aquaculture sector by means of awareness and specific training activities designed to promote the role of women in aquaculture and increase its visibility in the sector. Examples of these activities are included in the All-Atlantic pledge campaign on Women's Empowerment in Aquaculture led by ASTRAL.

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Fig. 1 World Ocean Day 2021: clean up with Makoko fishing community, thematic sessions, and waste upcycling activities. June 8th, (Lagos, Nigeria).

Fig. 2 Ideation Days 2022. February 28th (Terceira Island, Azores, Portugal)